

SMARANDACHE PASCAL DERIVED SEQUENCES

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Given a sequence say S_b . We call it the base sequence. We define a **Smarandache Pascal derived sequence S_d** as follows:

$$T_{n+1} = \sum_{k=0}^n {}^n C_k \cdot t_{k+1}, \text{ where } t_k \text{ is the } k^{\text{th}} \text{ term of the base sequence.}$$

Let the terms of the the base sequence S_b be

$$b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4, \dots$$

Then the Smarandache Pascal derived Sequence S_d

$d_1, d_2, d_3, d_4, \dots$ is defined as follows:

$$d_1 = b_1$$

$$d_2 = b_1 + b_2$$

$$d_3 = b_1 + 2b_2 + b_3$$

$$d_4 = b_1 + 3b_2 + 3b_3 + b_4$$

...

$$d_{n+1} = \sum_{k=0}^n {}^n C_k \cdot b_{k+1}$$

These derived sequences exhibit interesting properties for some base sequences.

Examples:

{1} $S_b \rightarrow 1, 2, 3, 4, \dots$ (natural numbers)

$S_d \rightarrow 1, 3, 8, 20, 48, 112, 256, \dots$ (Smarandache Pascal derived natural number sequence)

The same can be rewritten as

$$2 \times 2^{-1}, 3 \times 2^0, 4 \times 2^1, 5 \times 2^2, 6 \times 2^3, \dots$$

It can be verified and then proved easily that $T_n = 4(T_{n-1} - T_{n-2})$ for $n > 2$.

And also that $T_n = (n+1) \cdot 2^{n-2}$

{2} $S_b \rightarrow 1, 3, 5, 7, \dots$ (odd numbers)

$S_d \rightarrow 1, 4, 12, 32, 80, \dots$

The first difference $1, 3, 8, 20, 48, \dots$ is the same as the S_d for natural numbers.

The sequence S_d can be rewritten as

$$1 \cdot 2^0, 2 \cdot 2^1, 3 \cdot 2^2, 4 \cdot 2^3, 5 \cdot 2^4, \dots$$

Again we have $T_n = 4(T_{n-1} - T_{n-2})$ for $n > 2$. Also $T_n = n \cdot 2^{n-1}$.

{3} **Smarandache Pascal Derived Bell Sequence:**

Consider the Smarandache Factor Partitions (SFP) sequence for the square free numbers:

(The same as the **Bell number** sequence.)

$S_b \rightarrow 1, 1, 2, 5, 15, 52, 203, 877, 4140, \dots$

We get the derived sequence as follows

$S_d \rightarrow 1, 2, 5, 15, 52, 203, 877, 4140, \dots$

The **Smarandache Pascal Derived Bell Sequence** comes out to be the same. We

call it **Pascal Self Derived Sequence**. This has been established in ref. [1]
 In what follows, we shall see that this Transformation applied to Fibonacci
 Numbers gives beautiful results.

****{4} Smarandache Pascal derived Fibonacci Sequence:**

Consider the Fibonacci Sequence as the Base Sequence:

$$S_b \rightarrow 1, 1, 2, 3, 5, 8, 13, 21, 34, 55, 89, 114, 233, \dots$$

We get the following derived sequence

$$S_d \rightarrow 1, 2, 5, 13, 34, 89, 233, \dots \quad (\text{A})$$

It can be noticed that the above sequence is made of the alternate (even numbered
 terms of the sequence) Fibonacci numbers.

This gives us the following result on the Fibonacci numbers.

$$F_{2n} = \sum_{k=0}^n {}^n C_k \cdot F_k, \text{ where } F_k \text{ is the } k^{\text{th}} \text{ term of the base Fibonacci sequence.}$$

Some more interesting properties are given below.

If we take (A) as the base sequence we get the following derived sequence S_{dd}

$$S_{dd} \rightarrow 1, 3, 10, 35, 125, 450, 1625, 5875, 21250, \dots$$

An interesting observation is ,the first two terms are divisible by 5^0 , the next two
 terms by 5^1 , the next two by 5^2 , the next two by 5^3 and so on.

$$T_{2n} \equiv T_{2n-1} \equiv 0 \pmod{5^n}$$

On carrying out this division we get the following sequence i.e.

$$1, 3, 2, 7, 5, 18, 13, 47, 34, 123, 89, \dots \quad (\text{B})$$

The sequence formed by the odd numbered terms is

$$1, 2, 5, 13, 34, 89, \dots$$

which is again nothing but S_d (the base sequence itself).

Another interesting observation is every even numbered term of (B) is the sum of
 the two adjacent odd numbered terms. ($3 = 1+2$, $7 = 2 +5$, $18 = 5 + 13$ etc.)

CONJECTURE: Thus we have the possibility of another beautiful result on the
 Fibonacci numbers which of-course is yet to be established.

$$F_{2m+1} = (1/5^m) \sum_{r=0}^{2m+1} C_r \left(\sum_{k=0}^r C_k F_k \right)$$

Note: It can be verified that all the above properties hold good for the Lucas
 sequence (1 , 3, 4, 7, 11, . . .) as well.

Pascalisation of Fibonacci sequence with index in arithmetic progression:

Consider the following sequence formed by the Fibonacci numbers whose indexes
 are in A. P.

$F_1, F_{d+1}, F_{2d+1}, F_{3d+1}, \dots$ on pascalisation gives the following sequence

$$1, d.F_2, d^2.F_4, d^3.F_6, d^4.F_8, \dots, d^n.F_{2n}, \dots$$

for $d = 2$ and $d = 3$.

For $d = 5$ we get the following

Base sequence : $F_1, F_6, F_{11}, F_{16}, \dots$

$$1, 13, 233, 4181, 46368, \dots$$

Derived sequence: 1, 14, 260, 4920, 93200, . . . in which we notice that
 $260 = 20 \cdot (14 - 1)$, $4920 = 20 \cdot (260 - 14)$, $93200 = 4920 - 260$) etc . which suggests
the possibility of

Conjecture: The terms of the pascal derived sequence for $d = 5$ are given by
 $T_n = 20 \cdot (T_{n-1} - T_{n-2})$ ($n > 2$)

For $d = 8$ we get

Base sequence : $F_1, F_9, F_{17}, F_{25}, \dots$

$S_b \rightarrow 1, 34, 1597, 75025, \dots$

$S_d \rightarrow 1, 35, 1666, 79919, \dots$

$= 1, 35, (35-1) \cdot 7^2, (1666 - 35) \cdot 7^2, \dots$ etc. which suggests the possibility of

Conjecture: The terms of the pascal derived sequence for $d = 8$ are given by
 $T_n = 49 \cdot (T_{n-1} - T_{n-2})$, ($n > 2$)

Similarly we have Conjectures:

For $d = 10$, $T_n = 90 \cdot (T_{n-1} - T_{n-2})$, ($n > 2$)

For $d = 12$, $T_n = 18^2 \cdot (T_{n-1} - T_{n-2})$, ($n > 2$)

Note: There seems to be a direct relation between d and the coefficient of $(T_{n-1} - T_{n-2})$ (or the common factor) of each term which is to be explored.

{5} Smarandache Pascal derived square sequence:

$S_b \rightarrow 1, 4, 9, 16, 25, \dots$

$S_d \rightarrow 1, 5, 18, 56, 160, 432, \dots$

Or $1, 5 \times 1, 6 \times 3, 7 \times 8, 8 \times 20, 9 \times 48, \dots$, ($T_n = (n+3)t_{n-1}$), where t_r is the r^{th} term of Pascal derived natural number sequence.

Also one can derive $T_n = 2^{n-2} \cdot (n+3)(n)/2$.

{6} Smarandache Pascal derived cube sequence:

$S_b \rightarrow 1, 8, 27, 64, 125$

$S_d \rightarrow 1, 9, 44, 170, 576, 1792, \dots$

We have $T_n \equiv 0 \pmod{(n+1)}$.

Similarly we have derived sequences for higher powers which can be analyzed for patterns.

{7} Smarandache Pascal derived Triangular number sequence:

$S_b \rightarrow 1, 3, 6, 10, 15, 21, \dots$

$S_d \rightarrow 1, 4, 13, 38, 104, 272, \dots$

{8} Smarandache Pascal derived Factorial sequence:

$S_b \rightarrow 1, 2, 6, 24, 120, 720, 5040, \dots$

$S_d \rightarrow 1, 3, 11, 49, 261, 1631, \dots$

We can verify that $T_n = n \cdot T_{n-1} + \sum T_{n-2} + 1$.

Problem: Are there infinitely many primes in the above sequence?

Smarandache Pascal derived sequence of the k^{th} order.

Consider the natural number sequence again:

$S_b \rightarrow 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, \dots$ The corresponding derived sequence is

$S_d \rightarrow 2 \times 2^1, 3 \times 2^0, 4 \times 2^1, 5 \times 2^2, 6 \times 2^3, \dots$ With this as the base sequence we get the derived sequence denoted by S_{d2} as

S_{d2} or $S_{d2} \rightarrow 1, 4, 15, 54, 189, 648, \dots$ which can be rewritten as

$1, 4 \times 3^0, 5 \times 3^1, 6 \times 3^2, 7 \times 3^3 \dots$

similarly we get S_{d3} as $1, 5 \times 4^0, 6 \times 4^1, 7 \times 4^2, 8 \times 4^3, \dots$ which suggests the

possibility of the terms of S_{dk} , the k^{th} order Smarandache Pascal derived natural

number sequence being given by

$1, (k+2) \cdot (k+1)^0, (k+3) \cdot (k+1)^1, (k+4) \cdot (k+1)^2, \dots, (k+r) \cdot (k+1)^{r-2}$ etc. This can be proved by induction.

We can take an arithmetic progression with the first term 'a' and the common difference 'b' as the base sequence and get the derived k^{th} order sequences to generalize the above results.

Reference:[1] Amarnath Murthy, 'Generalization of Partition Function,. Introducing Smarandache Factor Partitions' SNJ, Vol. 11, No. 1-2-3,2000.